

the difference in NBOMD was because the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) in B degraded faster than in C. This was contributed by higher digestibility of cellulose and hemicellulose, the two components of NDF.

The difference between A and B was perhaps due to a combination of higher

neutral detergent solubles (NDS), higher crude protein (CP), and lower cell wall (NDF) contents for A. The higher NBOMD in A was attributed to the higher NDF ($r = 0.9$) and cellulose digestibility ($r = 0.7$) and CP content ($r = 0.66$). Varieties with lower NDF contained more CP.

The NBOMD of the three common varieties was similar during both years, indicating no year effect. The varieties were grown under the same agronomic conditions in the same soil, implying that the difference in NBOMD could only be because of their genetic makeup. ■

Heterosis in chemical composition and digestibility of rice straw

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The straw of 15 F_1 crosses and that of their 10 parents were collected from a rice breeding experiment. The chemical composition and nylon bag (72-h) dry matter digestibility (NBDMD) were determined for each (see table).

Crossing two varieties resulted in a hybrid with higher NBDMD than that of the parents, except for Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6. Eliminating the cross with negative heterosis (Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6) from heritability (h^2) estimation by regression gave h^2 values of 0.86 for NBDMD and 0.82 for nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD).

The crude protein (CP) content in most hybrids was greater than that of both or one of the parents. Both Narendra 118 and Pant Dhan 6 had

Chemical composition (%) and NBDMD (%) of rice straw from different parents and hybrids.

	Parents			Hybrids			
	CP	NDF	NBDMD	CP	NDF	NBDMD	NBOMD
IR58 ^a	4.2	70.1	47.1	—	—	—	—
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	4.9	65.2	51.7	52.9 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	4.9	69.5	49.9	51.0 ab
IET7613	4.7	68.6	49.9	5.4	68.2	54.6	55.7 c
UPR83-169	5.1	66.2	49.0	6.5	65.8	54.5	55.6 c
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	67.3	50.2	51.4 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	5.8	67.6	53.8	54.8 c
Narendra 118 ^a	5.1	69.2	48.0	—	—	—	—
UPR82-43	3.6	72.1	41.2	5.3	66.9	49.8	51.1 ab
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	6.0	67.7	50.7	51.8 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	6.5	66.5	52.2	53.4 bc
IET7613	4.7	68.6	45.9	6.1	70.6	52.0	53.0 bc
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	4.7	68.1	47.9	49.0 a
IET6223 ^a	4.4	66.6	45.1	—	—	—	—
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	5.3	66.7	51.2	52.3 b
IET7613	4.7	68.4	45.9	5.7	64.6	50.1	51.2 ab
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	68.5	49.7	50.9 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.8	49.3	6.0	69.0	52.2	53.4 bc

^aIR58, Narendra 118, and IET6223 were crossed with the varieties grouped below them to produce hybrids.

relatively higher dry matter digestibility (DMD) and CP, so no further improvement could be expected in the hybrids.

Polygenes, the combination of which seem to be identical in these two varieties, may control the CP content.

The positive correlation between CP and DMD and the simultaneous reduction in the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) of hybrids are desirable for improving the nutritive value of straw. ■

Allelic relationship among fertility-restoring genes in rice

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We studied the allelism for the restoring gene(s) present in purified testers received from IRRI. The five testers, IR24 (T_1), IR54742-22-19-3 (T_2), IR29723-143-3-2-1 (T_3), IR9761-19-1 (T_4), and ARC11353 (T_5), were tested for

Segregation pattern of pollen and spikelet fertilities in test cross F_1 progenies. Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Test cross	Total plants observed (no.)	Pollen fertility ^a		Spikelet fertility ^b	
		Fertile	Sterile	Fertile	Sterile
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_2$)	200	169	31	169	31
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_3$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_4$)	200	175	25	174	26
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_3$)	200	165	35	167	33
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_4$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_5$)	200	168	32	166	34
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_4$)	200	178	22	178	22
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_4 \times T_5$)	200	161	39	163	37

^aPollen fertility = fertility $\geq$ 60%, sterility = 0%. ^bSpikelet fertility = fertility $\geq$ 80%, sterility = 0%.